



Fig. 3. Deposited on the aluminum substrate Vanadium microparticles, which were ejected from the free surface of a foil with a thickness of 0.16 mm when exposed to 5 pulses of argon plasma. a – the surface of the original aluminum substrate; b – the X-ray spectrum from its surface; c, d, e - vanadium particles on the substrate surface; f - the x-ray spectrum in the particle region shown in fig. 3e.